

Coulometric Titration of Niobium in 1*F* Sulfuric Acid

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Manuscript received 30 September 1974; accepted 17 March 1975

A coulometric titration at constant current has been devised for Nb in 1*F* sulfuric acid. The titration was based on the oxidation of Nb(III) to Nb(V) by Fe(III) electrogenerated at a graphite anode. Both potentiometric and amperometric end points were used. The Nb(V) was prior reduced at a mercury cathode by exhaustive electrolysis at a current density of 15 ma/cm² for at least 10 hr. Ta, V, Ti and a working platinum anode interfered, but the separation of the potentials of Nb(V)/Nb(III) and Ti(IV)/Ti(II) permitted the titration of first Nb and then Ti. The average error for the titration of 0.30 to 13.00 mg of niobium in 100 ml of 1*F* sulfuric acid was +0.57%.

THE use of niobium in electronic tubes, breeder reactors, gas turbines, jet engines, and its proposed use in coins as a substitute for silver¹ has stimulated interest in accurate methods for its analysis. Niobium is generally determined gravimetrically,² colorimetrically,³ and polarographically,⁴⁻⁹. Volumetric analysis is not widely used because of its inconvenience and inaccuracy. Volumetric methods are based on the titration of Nb(III) in sulfuric acid with a standard solution of an oxidizing agent¹⁰⁻¹². The results of the determination of Nb(III) formed by reduction of Nb(V) in sulfuric acid with zinc amalgam are not reproducible.³ Electrolysis at a mercury cathode is the only reliable method for the reduction of Nb(V) to Nb(III) in dilute sulfuric acid. Niobium(III) solution is separated from mercury in the absence of oxygen before titration with an oxidizing agent. It was felt that a constant current coulometric method for the determination of Nb in sulfuric acid would, if developed, possess advantages compared to volumetric methods, since Nb can be determined in the electrolytic cell without any separation. Sulfuric acid was chosen as the first medium to use for the coulometric titration because the volumetric determination of Nb has been carried out principally in sulfuric acid.

Both reductimetry and oxidimetry were considered in designing a constant current coulometric titration of Nb in sulfuric acid. On the basis of its standard electrode potential¹³, Cr(II) should reduce Nb(V) in the acidic medium. Reductimetry, however, was soon eliminated on the basis that strong reducing ions like Cr(II) cannot be generated with 100%¹⁴ current efficiency in the acid solution. Electrogenerated Fe(III) was considered a promising intermediate for the oxidation of Nb(III). Therefore, the reaction :

forms the basis of the coulometric titration. Inspection of the electrode potentials for the two couples indicates that the reaction should be quantitative :

$$E^\circ \text{Fe(III)/Fe(II)} = +0.77 \text{ volt}$$
$$E^\circ \text{Nb(V)/Nb(III)} = 0.13 \text{ volt, log } K = 22$$

The study of the polarography of Nb and its controlled potential coulometry should suggest suitable conditions for the electrolytic reduction of Nb(V) at the mercury cathode and give evidence for the relative stability of Nb(III) in sulfuric acid. Values of half-wave potentials for the reduction of Nb(V) in sulfuric acid have been given in the literature¹⁵⁻¹⁶. However, no systematic measurement of these half-wave potentials as a function of sulfuric acid concentration has been reported. It has been found in this work (Figure 1) that reduction of Nb(V) yields a single wave in 5 to 10*F*

Fig 1. D. C. Polarograms of Nb (V) in H₂SO₄
I and III 7.5*F* and 15*F* H₂SO₄
II and IV 1.9700 × 10⁻⁸M Nb (V) in
7.5*F* and 15*F* H₂SO₄
respectively

sulfuric acid and two waves in 13 to 15*F* sulfuric acid. The single wave in 5 to 10*F* sulfuric acid constitutes the reaction: $\text{Nb(V)} + 2e \rightarrow \text{Nb(III)}$. The two waves in 13 to 15*F* sulfuric acid comprise successive reactions:

Since no wave due to the reduction of Nb(V) in less than 5*F* sulfuric acid was obtained, the polarography of Nb(V) in this concentration of sulfuric acid suggests that its reduction can be achieved by exhaustive electrolysis only. The controlled potential coulometry of Nb(V) was not pursued in sulfuric acid because the diffusion currents due to the reduction of Nb(V) or the oxidation of Nb(III) are not large in comparison with the residual currents of the background electrolyte prepared from reagent grade sulfuric acid.

It was anticipated that sulfuric acid might have to be abandoned for some other medium because of the tendency of Nb(V) to hydrolyze in dilute acids. Ethylenediaminetetraacetic acid (EDTA) was considered to be suitable complexing medium for devising a constant current titration of Nb because the polarography of Nb(V)-EDTA has been studied in detail by a number of workers⁴⁻⁷. The coulometric titration of Nb in EDTA will be described in a later publication.

Experimental

Apparatus: The apparatus used for the coulometric titration of Nb is shown in Figure 2, where the water-jacketed Cell A made by Scientific Glass Apparatus Co. (Catalog No. J-2478) was connected to Cell B, an adaptation from the literature^{1,7}. The construction of Cell B was adopted to improve the isolation of the anolyte from the catholyte through a salt bridge.

Figure 2. SET-UP FOR COULOMETRIC TITRATIONS

1. Gas outlet
2. Mercury seal
3. Salt bridge
4. Nitrogen inlet
5. Anode compartment
6. Stirrer
7. Mercury

8. Platinum contact
9. Teflon
10. Copper wire
11. Gas inlet
12. Thermometer
13. Like platinum electrodes
14. Finger condenser
15. Graphite anode
16. Salt bridge
17. Gas outlet
18. Bridge
19. Cathode compartment
20. Magnetic bar covered with teflon
21. Anode compartment

The cathode compartment of Cell B possessed an effective volume of about 140 cm³ and the surface area of the mercury electrode when stationary was 19.6 cm². A glass tube fitted with a two-way stopcock was joined to the base of this compartment. Through one hole, mercury could be removed; and through the other, mercury could be added. Contact was made by a copper wire dipping in the mercury. The nitrogen inlet consisted of a glass tube enclosing a coarse glass sintered disc to filter the gas and ended in a capillary through a No. 10 standard taper joint. The gas outlet was a glass tube fused to the side of the wall near the top of the cathode compartment. Through the stopper were mounted a finger condenser, a graphite rode, a K₂SO₄-agar bridge, a thermometer, an inlet for the reduced FeSO₄·(NH₄)₂SO₄·6H₂O solution, and two Pt electrodes having a surface area of 1.5 cm². The cell was filled with requisite quantity of Hg before the addition of Nb(V) solution. Stirring was effected with a magnetic stirrer.

The bridge was about 12.5 cm long and 2.5 cm in diameter and had a fine sintered glass disc located near the anode compartment together with a coarse sintered glass disc near the cathode compartment. The cathode compartment and the bridge were provided with stopcocks to drain out the electrolyte after the experiment was completed, and they were filled again with air-free 1*F* sulfuric acid before the Nb solution was transferred to the cell. The level of the electrolyte in the bridge and in the cathode compartment was kept higher than in the anode compartment. The cathode was 18 gauge platinum wires; a 3.5-cm length dipped below a glass tubing through which it was fused. The resistance of the cell, when filled with 1*F* sulfuric acid, was about 300 ohms.

Nitrogen was freed of oxygen by passing it through a CrCl₂ solution, prepared by adding 20 g of amalgamated Zn to 175 ml of 0.1*F* CrCl₃ solution in 1*F* HCl, and then was bubbled through water to remove any Cr²⁺ and Cr³⁺ carried by spray to the cell.

The power for electrolysis was provided by a DC power supply, Model NFA, made by Electro Products Laboratories, Chicago. A multimeter, Model 630-NA, of the Triplet Company indicated the current used for the reduction of Nb(V) solution. The constant current source was constructed according to the description given by Reilly and coworkers^{1,8}. The current for each run performed with the above current source was in the range of 20 to 24 ma. A low constant current of 3 to

4 ma was drawn from two Burgess heavy-duty B batteries connected in parallel with a proper resistor in series. The current was calculated from Ohm's law by measuring the IR drop across a 50 ohm $\pm 0.05\%$ precision resistor with a Leeds and Northrup type K potentiometer. An electric digital timer supplied by Precision Scientific Co. was used as the interval meter, and could be read to 0.1 second. The timing and constant current circuits were synchronized by a Leeds and Northrup precision DPDT switch.

Reagents: Preparation of Nb(V) and Ta(V) solutions in sulphuric Acid. Stock solutions of Nb(V) and Ta(V) in sulfuric Acid were prepared from 99.85% Nb₂O₅ (Kawecki Chemical Company) according to Schoeller².

Procedure: Aliquots of Nb(V) in H₂SO₄ were added to Cell B, the cathode compartment and the bridge of which were filled previously with the same concentration of sulfuric acid as in the anode compartment. The solution in the anode compartment was deaerated and stirred. The potential of the solution before and after electrolysis was measured with the stirred mercury pool versus a saturated mercury (I) sulfate electrode (S. M. E.). In the beginning of the electrolysis of Nb(V) solution, Cell A was connected to Cell B by turning the stopper to the proper position. A brisk stream of nitrogen was admitted to Cell A and forced to flow towards Cell B by closing the outlet of Cell A. It was assumed that no oxygen was left in C after a deaeration of one or two minutes. The requisite amount of Hg was added to Cell A and its anode compartment was filled with saturated K₂SO₄ solution. Approximately 100 ml of 0.4*F* FeSO₄·(NH₄)₂SO₄·6H₂O in the desired concentration of H₂SO₄ was reduced under a N₂ atmosphere at a stirred mercury pool with a current density of about 2 ma/cm². Electrolysis was continued until the solution yielded a negative test for Fe³⁺ ion—that is, no pink color was visible when a 0.5 ml-aliquot was mixed with 2 to 3 ml of 1*F* KCNS solution. Whenever a coulometric titration was to be performed, the current to both cells was switched off, mercury was withdrawn from Cell A, and the electrolyzed FeSO₄·(NH₄)₂SO₄·6H₂O was forced to flow into Cell B. The volume of the solution transferred was read from the calibration on the anodic compartment of Cell B. A constant current was passed through Cell B, using a graphite anode and a platinum cathode. The circuit was switched to the lower constant current when about 95% of the titration had been completed.

The current efficiency for the electrogeneration of Fe(III) in various concentrations of H₂SO₄ at a graphite electrode was determined from current potential curves to be 100 percent. The current efficiency was also checked from the coulometric titration of electro-generated Fe³⁺ at a graphite anode using Ti³⁺ as the intermediate.

The potentiometric end point (zero current method) was detected by measuring the potential of the stirred mercury pool versus S. M. E. with a V. T. V. M. It was not found useful to measure the potentials to better than 0.01 volt because the potentials near the end point were not steady. Two Pt foils, each having an area of 1.5 cm², were employed for the amperometric end point detection. Platinum electrodes were employed in this system even though it was known that a working Pt surface^{1,9} could catalyze the reaction:

Since the number of coulombs passed through the electrodes prior to the end point is small, any amount of Nb(III) oxidized would be negligible. A potential difference of 0.15 volt was impressed across them, and the current was measured with a galvanometer having a rated sensitivity of about 0.12 $\mu\text{a/mm}$. During the titration, only a slight residual current registered because the electrodes of the indicating system are not depolarized by the small applied emf. However, after the end point, iron(III) ions are generated and the following reversible reactions take place at the indicating electrodes:

These reactions led to the increase of current.

Suitable conditions for the reduction of Nb(V) in sulfuric acid are given below.

Concentration of Sulfuric Acid: It was concluded from a number of trials that 1*F* sulfuric acid would be used for the constant current coulometric determination of niobium.

Current Density and Duration of Electrolysis: Tomicek and coworkers¹¹ do not spell out the current density and surface area of their mercury cathode, but indicate that a 24-volt battery was used without any resistance in series. The value of 24 volts across the cell was taken as a rough guide, and it was found that a current density of 15 ma/cm² at the mercury cathode was adequate for the electroreduction of Nb(V) in sulfuric acid. Low results were obtained when a current density of 3 ma/cm² was used at the mercury cathode for reduction. Quantitative reduction of Nb(V) in 26% H₂SO₄ is claimed¹¹ to have been achieved in six to eight hours. However, in our investigation in 1*F* H₂SO₄, it was found that the electrolysis at the mercury cathode should be carried out exhaustively for at least ten hours to achieve quantitative results. In an attempt to lower the reduction time, the current density of the mercury cathode was raised from 15 to 60 ma/cm², corresponding to the current strength used by Treadwell and Nieriker¹², but the results became erratic at the higher current density.

Results and Discussion

Typical results for the coulometric titrations of niobium are shown in Table 1.

TABLE 1—SOME TYPICAL RESULTS FOR CONSTANT CURRENT COULOMETRIC DETERMINATION OF NB IN 1*F* SULFURIC ACID USING AMPEROMETRIC AND/OR POTENTIOMETRIC EACH POINT DETECTION

Nb Taken (mg)	Nb Found (Average) (mg)	No. of Trials	Mean Error %
0.33	0.38	1	0.0
2.15	2.16*	3	+0.5
4.29	4.32	1	+0.7
4.26	4.33*	3	+1.6
4.31	4.33	2	+0.7
4.73	4.73	2	0.0
6.42	6.49*	2	+1.1
8.63	8.65*	3	+0.2
9.45	9.46	2	+0.1
12.97	13.08	2	+0.8

Mean Percent Error = 0.57 (overall)

*Potentiometric end point; others, potentiometric and amperometric.

INTERFERENCES: Effect of the Presence of a Pt Surface. During the work with H₂SO₄ electrolyte, the need to substitute graphite for Pt as the anode material was confirmed by titrations that compared both materials. Kiehl and coworkers^{1,9} found that a Pt surface catalyzes the reaction between Nb(III) and H⁺. However, in the studies reported in this paper, a Pt gauze electrode was found to influence titrations of Nb only when working. If the Pt gauze was immersed in the electrolyte, but not operated as an electrode, no perceptible effect was noted.

Effect of the Presence of Ti(IV): It was found that about eight hours is sufficient for the electroreduction of Ti(SO₄)₂ solution and Nb(V) in H₂SO₄ at the mercury cathode. Shortening of the reduction period might be due to the formation of Ti²⁺ which would reduce Nb(V).

The formation of titanium(II) could account for high results obtained in initial trials. Hence, the reduced solutions were allowed to stand for about an hour before the coulometric titration was carried out. During this time, titanium(II) would react with hydrogen ion:

The reduced solutions containing Nb(III) and Ti(III), when titrated oxidimetrically, gave two breaks in the potentiometric curve, the first corresponding to Nb(III) to Nb(V) and the second to Ti(III) to Ti(IV).

The results obtained from such titrations are given in Table 2. It is seen from Table 2 that the results for the determination of Nb and Ti are no better than the results of the coulometric titration of Nb alone.

TABLE 2—RESULTS OF COULOMETRIC TITRATION OF NB AND Ti IN 1*F* H₂SO₄

Duration of Electro-reduction Prior to Titration (C.d. = 15 ma/cm ²) (hours)	Nb Taken (mg)	Ti Taken (mg)	Nb Found (mg)	Percent Error of Nb	Ti Found (mg)	Percent Error of Ti
10.75	4.32	1.90	4.29	-0.69	1.94	+2.11
13	1.74	3.80	1.69	-2.87	3.80	0.0
11	3.49	3.80	3.44	-1.43	3.79	-0.26

Effect of Presence of Vanadium (V): The exhaustive electrolysis of vanadium(V) in sulfuric acid at a mercury cathode yields V(II). From a survey of the literature, it was found that V has not been determined coulometrically using the oxidation step for V(II) to V(III). However, the potential of the V(III)/V(II) couple lies close to the potential of the Nb(V)/Nb(III) couple in H₂SO₄. Hence, V interferes with the determination of Nb using the oxidation step. In several exploratory experiments, stoichiometric results were not obtained for the oxidation of V(II).

Effect of Presence of Ta(V): Tomicek and coworkers¹¹ reported that Ta(V) in 26% sulfuric acid is not reduced at the mercury cathode. However, the work carried out in this laboratory showed that Ta(V) is definitely reduced in 1*F* and 26% sulfuric acid. Thus its presence leads to high results in attempts to titrate Nb.

The solution containing Ta(V) alone in 1*F* H₂SO₄ acid was reduced over a mercury cathode, and it was found that the color of the reduced solution was light brown and the potential was more reducing than Nb(III) solution. The results were not reproducible when reduced Ta solutions were titrated with electro-generated Fe³⁺ at a graphite anode. Likewise, when Ta and Nb were reduced together, the results were not reproducible. From a number of exploratory experiments with solutions containing Ta(V) alone, the valence state of the reduced species could not be readily established. Subsequently, the determination of niobium in the presence of Ta has been accomplished in EDTA solutions which will be described at a later date.

Acknowledgement

I am thankful to Dr. Hershel McDowell and Dr. Georg Ng both of Federal City College for reviewing this manuscript.

References

1. *Chem. Eng. News*, 1965, Feb. 22, p. 19.
2. W. R. SCHOELLER., "The Analytical Chemistry of Tantalum and Niobium, The Analysis of Their Minerals and the Application of Tannin in Gravimetric Analysis," Chapman and hall, London, 1937.

3. W. T. ELWELL and D.F. WOOD., *Anal. Chim. Acts*, 1962, **26**, 1.
4. D. J. BRINDLEY and J. LUCAS., *Analyst*, 1960, **85**, 877.
5. D. J. FERRETT and G. W. C. MILNER., *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1956, 1186
6. J. H. KENNEDY., *Anal. Chem.*, 1961, **33**, 943.
7. R. KIRBY and H. FREISER., *Anal. Chem.* 1963, **35**, 122.
8. S. MARCHIDAN, C. DRAGULESCU and GH. FACSKO.. *Rev. Roum. Chim.* 1971, **16**, 813. *Chem. Abs.* **75**, 70989 B.
9. G. POPA, R. RUDOLF, I. CAZACU., *An Univ. Bucuresti, Chim*, 1970, **19**, 9, *Chem. Abs* **75**, 125883.
10. S. J. KIEHL and DAVID HART., *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1928, **50**, 1608.
11. O. TOMICEK, K. SPURNY, L. JERMAN, and V HOLECEK., *Coll. Czech, Chem. Commun.*, 1953, **18**, 757.
12. W. D. TREADWELL and R. NIERIKER., *Helv. Chim. Acta*, 1942, **25**, 474.
13. J. J. LINGANE., "Electroanalytical Chemistry," Interscience Publishers, New York, 2nd Ed., 1958.
14. A. M. HARTLEY., Ph. D. THESIS, Harvard University (1955).
15. P. BUNCAK., *Chem. Prumysl*, 1961, **11**, 634, *Chem. Abs.* **56**, 7992.
16. E. I. KRYLOV and V. S. KOLEVATOVA., *Zhur Prikladn. Khim.*, 1956, **29**, 1292. *Chem. Abs.* **50**, 15282.
17. J. K. TAYLOR and S. W. SMITH., *J. Res. Nat. Bur., Stand.*, 1959, **63A**, 153.
18. C. N. REILLEY, W. D. COOKE and N. H. FURMAN. *Anul. Chem.*, 1951, **23**, 1030.
19. S. J. KIEHL, R. L. FOX and H. B. HARDT., *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.* 1937, **59**, 2395.